

VPP4-DMP: A research project on adults' professional development and the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia

Version 2

Description

This document is an updated version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the research study (2023–2026), conducted within the State Research Programme project Education, No. VPP-IZM-Izglītība-2023/4-0001, entitled “Elaboration of evidence-based solutions for effective professional competence development of adults and assessment of the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia”. The DMP has been implemented as a living document and is managed using the Argos DMP tool. Significant updates made during the lifetime of the project will be uploaded to Zenodo. The DMP will be revised in line with the project’s periodic evaluations or more frequently, if required. The aim of the project is to develop an evidence-based framework and practical solutions for efficient and effective adult professional development and for the transfer of its results into practice. In addition, the project offers tools for assessing the impact of professional development on practice at organisational and system levels in Latvia. The study is organised as a mixed-methods, design-based research project. The purpose of data generation and collection is to obtain both quantitative and qualitative data in order to achieve the project’s objectives. All data generation and collection activities comply with EU ethical and legal requirements, as well as with applicable national ethical and legal regulations. The research project has collected and generated the following types of data:

1. Video recordings, transcripts, and coded materials from focus group discussions with representatives of key adult education and professional development service providers (e.g. higher education institutions, VET institutions, training centres, and schools as learning organisations); recipients of adult education and professional development services (i.e. adult learners from a range of occupational fields and sectors); and experts

(e.g. representatives of NGOs, municipalities, and national-level education policy institutions) (Dataset 1).

2. Survey data collected from adult learners using online questionnaires (CAWI) and telephone interviews (CATI) to assess the current state of implementation of adult professional competence development and its transfer into practice in Latvia, including, for example, adults' motivations, behaviours, habits, and opportunities when choosing professional competence development activities (Dataset 2).

This research has received the ethical approval of the Ethics Committee for Research in Humanities and Social Sciences of the University of Latvia, Ethical approval No. 71-43/121, September 24, 2024.

Funder

Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Latvia

Grant

The State research programme "Education", project No. VPP-IZM-Izglītība-2023/4-0001

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Riga Technical University, Ventspils University
of Applied Sciences

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: VPP4-DMP: A research project on adults' professional development and the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Latvia

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Project: Elaboration of evidence-based solutions for effective professional competence development of adults and assessment of the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

A focus-group discussion dataset regarding adults' professional development and the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia (dataset 1)

The dataset contains video recordings, transcripts, and coded materials from focus-group discussions with representatives of key adult education and professional development service providers (e.g. higher education institutions, VET institutions, training centres, and schools as learning organisations); recipients of adult education and professional development services (employers and employees representing eight fields of economic activity with a higher proportion of employed individuals in Latvia, such as public administration and defence; education; health and social care; wholesale and retail trade; transport and storage; agriculture, forestry, and fishing; construction; and manufacturing); and experts (e.g. representatives of NGOs, municipalities, and national-level education policy institutions).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Fourteen focus-group discussions were conducted with the project's main target groups—28 experts, 33 service providers, and 68 service recipients—between November and December 2024. The discussions were held remotely via MS Teams and Zoom and aimed to identify the current situation in the field of professional development and the transfer of its outcomes into practice in Latvia. These

activities were carried out under Task 2.3 and Task 2.4 of Work Package 2: (1) conducting focus-group interviews with different target groups on how professional competence development is transferred into practice in Latvia; and (2) organising discussions of the findings with experts from various governmental and non-governmental organisations.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Other

videorecords

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- MP3
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Only to the project research team.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

This dataset is expected to be not shared and reusable, it will be used only for the project purposes (only to the project research team). The personal data / sensitive information obtained during the videorecording (including participants names and physical presence) will not be shared and re-used.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MP3 player

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Videorecords could be coded in AQUAD, NVivo or using any other qualitative data processing and analysis software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

License is not specified because this dataset is expected to be not shared and reusable, it will be used only for the project purposes.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

The personal data / sensitive information obtained during the videorecording (including participants names and physical presence) will not be shared and re-used.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The date is not specified because this dataset is expected to be not shared and reusable, it will be used only for the project purposes.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Svetlana Surikova (0000-0002-3025-6344)

As Project Manager, Svetlana Surikova is responsible for overseeing the process, providing guidance, and ensuring alignment with other project activities. Data description, processing, and analysis were carried out by Svetlana Surikova, Sanita Baranova, Dita Nīmante, and Gunta Siliņa-Jasjukeviča (UL); Inese Lūsēna-Ezera (RTU Liepaja); and Zane Zonberga, Sanita Lasmane, and Una Libkovska (VUAS).

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

The data obtained during the research have been stored in a safe infrastructure and protected by passwords and firewalls.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The personal data / sensitive information obtained during the videorecording (including participants names and physical presence) will not be shared.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

Personal data obtained within the project will include any information which relates to an identified or identifiable natural person. Completely anonymised data does not fall under the category of personal data (as from the moment it has been completely anonymised). The project team will collect and process data only if and insofar as it is necessary for the research. The research team will obtain the necessary notifications/authorisations for collecting and processing the data (including specific authorisations, if applicable), as well as free and fully informed consent of the data subjects concerned. All personal data will be anonymised in transcripts. In some cases (e.g., original videorecords with participants names and physical presence), the security measures to prevent unauthorised access to this information will be implemented according to the Latvia's normative acts as well as the ethical standards of the project lead partner. The personal data / sensitive

information obtained during the research will be stored in a safe infrastructure and protected by passwords and firewalls.

A survey dataset regarding adults' professional development and the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia (dataset 2)

The dataset contains information obtained from a study on adults' professional development and the transfer of learning outcomes into practice in Latvia. It includes a description of the research methodology (general information, the survey questionnaire with an accompanying codebook, descriptions of the sampling and weighting procedures, and a fieldwork report), as well as respondents' answers (raw data). The data reflect adults' motivation, behavioural patterns, habits, and opportunities in selecting professional competence development activities and applying them in practice, together with factors that hinder participation in professional development. The aim of the research was to investigate adults' motivation, behaviour, habits, and opportunities in selecting and transferring professional competence development into practice, in order to assess the current situation in the field of adult professional development in Latvia. The survey involved employed and self-employed residents of Latvia aged 16 to 65. To ensure the representativeness of the data by age, gender, ethnicity, region, level of education, and economic sector, a combination of online surveys (CAWI) and telephone interviews (CATI) was used. In total, data were collected from 1,000 respondents, representing the adult labour force of Latvia. Fieldwork was conducted between 11 March and 14 April 2025, and the dataset was published in a repository for further scientific analysis and for use in policy planning, research, and the improvement of education quality.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

A representative survey of adult learners was conducted between 11 March and 14 April 2025 to identify up-to-date situation in the field of professional development and the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia within the Task 2.5 of Work package 2 - to carry out an assessment of the current situation in the implementation of professional competence development for adults and its transfer to practice in Latvia, identifying, for example, the motivations, behaviours, habits and opportunities of individuals in choosing professional competence development.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- SAV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

3

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers, adult education (including professional development) providers, policy makers in adult and continuing education, MA and PhD students, governmental institutions (e.g., State labor inspectorate), non-governmental organisations (e.g., Employer's confederation of Latvia; trade unions), etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Metadata can be exported in eight different formats

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period will be applied until the scientific articles are submitted for publication and published as well as the final project assessment is finalised (i.e., till 01.07.2027.)

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV repository

<https://dv.dataverse.lv/>

DataverseLV is a secure, multidisciplinary research data repository in Latvia, supported by academic institutions. Built on Harvard's open-source Dataverse software, it enables open discovery, management, sharing, and preservation of research data. DataverseLV is Latvia's research data repository that offers a secure and reliable environment for storing, publishing, and sharing research data in accordance with FAIR principles and open science requirements. The repository hosts datasets produced by Latvian researchers. The repository is being integrated into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to enhance the data availability and interoperability on an international scale. DataverseLV Digital Preservation Policy has been described here

<https://dataverse.lv/en/dataverselv-digital-preservation-policy/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible with most of the software tools, including MS Excel, IBM SPSS Statistics, coding platforms (such as Python, R) and others.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data have been stored in open data formats (CSV, TXT, and PDF). The CSV format is widely supported by most applications that handle tabular data. In addition, SAV and XLS files have been stored, making the data accessible using SPSS and Microsoft Excel software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

It would be appreciated that this dataset is used/cited also in other studies.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-07-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2031-12-21

All data will be maintained for a minimum 5 years after the completion of the project.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data have been processed and published according to FAIR principles and best practice guidelines. After the project, the project lead partner will ensure periodic quality assessment procedures (in case of necessity, new versions of the datasets will be published). Quality improvements may be made also when the dataset is reused by third parties, taking into account their recommendations. Quality assurance will be ensured according to internal policy and procedure of the project lead partner.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

All staff costs will be covered within the project No. VPP-IZM-Izglītība-2023/4-0001 "Elaboration of evidence-based solutions for effective professional competence development of adults and assessment of the transfer of its results into practice in Latvia" within the State Research Programme "Education".

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Svetlana Surikova (0000-0002-3025-6344)

Svetlana Surikova as a project manager will be responsible for overseeing the process, guidance and alignment with other activities. Data description, processing and analysis will be done by Aleksandrs Koļesovs and Svetlana Surikova (UL) and Inese Lūsēna-Ezera (RTU Liepaja).

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Costs for reuse and long-term preservation after the project will be covered by the project lead partner's institution.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

All data have been stored in the DataverseLV repository. In accordance with the DataverseLV Digital Preservation Policy, as described at <https://dataverse.lv/en/dataverselv-digital-preservation-policy/>, the infrastructure is maintained in compliance with information security standards and national regulations. The LVRTC Service Level Agreement (SLA) is developed and implemented in accordance with Cabinet Instruction No. 5 of 8 November 2022, "Procedure for Ensuring the State Electronic Communications Service Centre." Secure authentication, role-based access control, firewalls, encrypted data transfer, and auditing mechanisms are employed. Administrative access is strictly limited, and emergency access is permitted only in defined cases under the SLA. Compliance with data protection requirements is ensured through clearly defined roles and processes.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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